

“AH WRONG SPEECH”: PERSUASION OF GRAMMAR USED IN PRESIDENT JOKO WIDODO’S SPEECH AT THE ECOSPERITY WEEK SPEECH IN SINGAPORE

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Abstract

This article is an analysis of the nature of propositions built in President Joko Widodo's persuasive speech about investment in the nation's capital from the perspective of mood analysis. This research also reveals how the speaker divides ethos, pathos and logos to the audience. This research uses discourse analysis with a qualitative approach to see how President Joko Widodo structures ethos, pathos and logos clauses grammatically. The results show that 1) ethos clauses are built with a declarative mood to show his credibility; 2) pathos clauses are formed with a declarative mood with the realization of the statement function and imperative mood to arouse the emotions of the audience; 3) logos clauses are structured with a declarative mood to provide a statement of the basis of the argumentation he conveyed.

Keywords: Grammar, Persuasion, President Joko Widodo, Speech.

INTRODUCTION

Language in politics is a tool that has the ability to influence certain beliefs and interests (Al-Khawaldeh et al., 2023). In speech, language as a medium of expression has persuasive elements that have the aim of inviting, convincing and persuading listeners about what is conveyed (Keraf, 2008). Persuasive speech has the main purpose to convince the audience and be persuaded in the discussion of the speech delivered. Persuasive speech has the main purpose of convincing the audience and being persuaded in the subject matter of the speech delivered. In political discourse, presidential speeches have a very important position (Noermanzah et al., 2018).

Grammar analysis in state speeches is needed to find out the techniques applied by someone in convincing listeners in terms of the grammar chosen (Power, 1998). According to Habermas, speech will form a coordination between the speaker and the listener in a dialogical orientation towards the validity of what is conveyed (Thibault & Theo, 1996). The form of grammar can shape social cognitive processes such as attribute delineation, inference and one's perception of something (Douglas & Sutton, 2003; Karasawa & Mass, 2008; Semin & Fiedler, 1988, 1991; Chicoka et al., 2016). When viewed at the state speech, the use of persuasive grammar is a common thing applied by the President to invite or move listeners to do something. The use of this grammar can be seen from Joko Widodo's state speech at Ecosperity Week in Singapore. This research aims to investigate the nature of propositions contained in the opening of President Joko Widodo's speech on June 7, 2023 in Singapore (Widodo, 2023). This research is viewed from the point of view of Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL).

Joko Widodo's speech at Ecosperity Week in Singapore was persuasive because it invited the audience to start thinking and deciding who will lead Indonesia in 2024 and to secure Singapore's investment in Indonesia. This speech drew considerable

attention because of the political jokes that triggered reactions from some circles. Jokowi's joke in a year that will enter the political period is a consideration to be analyzed further. In several studies there has been a lot of empirical data stating that humor has a role to determine communication that can attract audiences, word play and humor tactics serve to generate "advertising agenda setting (Camilo, 2008; Panke, 2013).

This research uses a grammatical approach to analyze Aristotle's rhetorical devices in the form of ethos, pathos, and logos. This approach was chosen because previous research analyzed the power of words, pragmatics, social and psychological aspects using this instrument (eg Braet, 1992; Higgins & Walker, 2012). The analysis was conducted with lexicogramatics consisting of lexical features, phrases and clause features (Crawford et al., 2018). The analysis was carried out using lexicogramatics on the main clauses in President Joko Widodo's speech which aims to identify the interpersonal relationships that are formed between the speaker and the listener and how the mood system is used to create ethos, pathos and logos.

Mood determines the success of forming ethos, pathos and logos. This means that mood influences the persuasive power that the speaker wants to convey to the listener. This analysis will produce a comprehensive view of how ethos, pathos and logos are structurally formed in a persuasive speech.

METHODS

This research is a discourse analysis with a qualitative approach to review how President Joko Widodo formulates and forms ethos, pathos and logos grammatically. This research takes the data source from the President's Speech at Ecosperity Week on June 2023 in Singapore which is taken from www.setneg.go.id. This speech contains 42 sentences consisting of 11 minor sentences and 27 major sentences. In this study, a simple complex sentence is counted as one clause, a compound sentence consisting of two major clauses is counted as two clauses and the rest depends on the main clause that forms the sentence.

This clause will be classified into each element of persuasion in the form of ethos, pathos and logos. The analysis was carried out by exploring the type of mood and function of speech as well as mood elements (subject, predicate, complement and adjective) that support elements of persuasion (ethos, pathos, logos).

RESULT & DISCUSSION

1. Result

President Joko Widodo uses one clause (a) to build an ethos which is conveyed in a declarative mood. Declarative sentences have the function of stating facts based on experiences they have had. President Joko Widodo assured that the statement he made was information whose credibility could be justified. President Joko Widodo showed himself as a person who has extensive experience in the topic of the speech being discussed. This action was carried out in the hope that his listeners could believe the statements he stated logically.

Specifically, the subject of the clause is formed as a personal subject with the pronoun "I". He uses the word "I" to inform the listener that "it is him", not someone else. This shows that he was the one who did this and implicitly states his credibility. The ethos

clause will help him state that he has considered all the concerns that investors have in investing their shares in the capital city of the archipelago.

President Joko Widodo communicates his credibility in the final element of the clause which uses positive polarity. This polarity gives positive validity to the proportion and helps it establish a positive atmosphere towards its audience. This polarity will help the listener to agree with his statement and state that "yes, he does understand it" (that he has a business background). The form of mood and ethos clauses from President Jokowi's speech are shown in table 1.

Table 1: Types of mood and realization of the function of the ethos clause in President Joko Widodo's speech

Mood Type	Realization Technique	Function	Example
Statement	Declarative Facts	Presenting personal experiences (in a positive way)	(a) "I am also a businessman" (clause 27)

In shaping the emotions of his audience (pathos), President Joko Widodo generally uses declarative mood clauses and occasionally uses imperative mood. The declarative mood used by Joko Widodo has clauses that vary from statements of opinion, statements and indirect requests. The imperative mood is shown according to its function, namely a direct request. The following are the types of mood and the realization of the speech function of the pathos clause which are presented in table 2.

Table 2: Type of mood in the realization of the speech function of pathos in President Joko Widodo's speech

Mood Type	Speech Function Realization	Technique	Example
Declarative	Statement of Opinion	Convey evaluative opinions	(b) "I know, house prices here are very high recently, maybe living in the archipelago could be an option" (clause 17)
	Statement	Affirm commitment	(c) "Indonesia has a serious commitment to the energy transition" (clause 33)
	Statement	Affirm hope	(d) "There is enormous potential to produce green products from green industries which are currently prioritized..." (clause 36)
	Indirect Requests	Asserting a request to do something.	(e) "Because we believe that economic success and sustainability must be done together" (clause 31)
Imperative	Direct Request	An invitation to do something	(f) "...I would like to take this opportunity to ask you who will win the presidential election next year" (clause 7) (g) "...You just have to participate and join our dollars to become a country with an economy worth trillions of dollars" (clause 44)

President Jokowi shows clauses indicating mood in two types of mood, namely declarative and imperative mood. Declarative mood clauses are predominantly indicated by statements. Indirect requests are only expressed in one clause as in (e). The declarative mood has four different realizations of speech functions including;

First, it has the function of stating an opinion which shows a belief or assessment about something or someone. The delivery technique is used with evaluative opinions as in (a) Jokowi uses a negative declarative mood by stating that house prices in Singapore are very high. This is an evaluation and strategy made by Jokowi to attract listeners' attention to the high house prices in Singapore.

Second, the declarative mood shown by President Joko Widodo through statements. This clause is used by President Joko Widodo to convey to listeners about the commitment and potential that Indonesia has. There are four techniques he uses, namely;

- 1). Affirm commitment; and
- 2). Affirm hope.

The first technique, namely emphasizing commitment, can be seen in (c). President Joko Widodo demonstrated this by giving the audience confidence that he has a big commitment to the energy transition. In touching the audience's emotions, he uses the word "commitment" to express his sincerity. The clause has the main objective of confirming that "he undertakes to implement it". He uses clauses that evoke a positive attitude from the audience towards President Joko Widodo's commitment to realizing the energy transition.

The second technique is to confirm the expectations seen in (d). This technique is used to build emotions of anticipation (waiting for something to happen positively). President Joko Widodo said that there is great potential in Indonesia and it is ready to be processed into green products. Green products are a priority in the industrial downstream sector which will support Indonesia's development.

Third, lexicographically, President Joko Widodo also uses the declarative mood to ask someone to do something indirectly. In several of his speeches, he asked for the audience's agreement to do good things together. Clause (e) shows his request to investors in Singapore to invest their shares in Indonesia. President Joko Widodo asked the audience to agree that cooperation between Indonesia and investors is needed to create economic success and sustainability.

In building Pathos, President Joko Widodo also uses clauses with an imperative mood to make a direct request for the audience to do something, as seen in (f) and (g). The technique used in (f) is an explicit request. President Joko Widodo uses the subject clause "I" which shows that he is directly asking about something he wants to know.

In the imperative mood shown in (g) it is done using a request technique with the word "must". The word must show that President Joko Widodo is giving orders directly to his audience. The subject clause which uses the word "you" and the first person pronoun "we" shows that the personal audience must join a group to make it stronger and more stable.

In shaping the mood of the audience, President Jokowi often uses pronouns as subject clauses including "we", "me" and "us". The word "we" which is inclusive is used 5 times and the word we is used exclusively 8 times. The word "we" is used inclusively to include involvement between the audience and the Indonesian Government in processing Indonesia's natural resources, such as "We have new energy potential...". The inclusive pronoun "we" is used 8 times. The word "we" inclusively refers to the

Indonesian government in managing natural resources and building the future city of the Indonesian capital, as in (e). and (g).

President Joko Widodo generally uses positive polarity but there are several negative polarities. He uses positive polarity when talking about economic commitment and investment. He uses negative polarity when talking about the high house prices in Singapore. The sentence forms in the clauses used vary from past, present and future. The past tense is used by President Joko Widodo to convey facts about the expensive cost of living in Singapore and the emotions of the audience so that they can invest in the capital city of the archipelago as a choice to live in. The present tense is conveyed in conveying the development of the capital city of the archipelago as in the sentence "Currently construction is underway...will be completed next year" (clause 18). The future tense is used to convey the emotional impact of his investment, as in "...join us to become a trillion-dollar economy." (clause 44).

To build mood, President Joko Widodo begins clauses with additional words and subjects. He uses additional words to precede clauses for two main reasons, namely: for compactness, he uses additional conjunctive words "but", "and" and "so". It is used to emphasize to the audience the facts represented by additional words (indirect, mood and comment). For example, in "So, I suggest you don't take too long." The comment caption "suggest not to take too long" tells the audience that investment in the capital of the archipelago has a lot of interest and convinces the audience not to waste any more time. This sentence is used to evoke positive sentiment in the audience towards Indonesia's sustainable economic development.

In forming the logos (logic) of the audience, President Joko Widodo uses several clauses presented in a declarative mood as statements of fact. This is explained in table 3.

Table 3: Types of Mood and Realization of Speech Functions in President Joko Widodo's Logos Clause.

Mood Type	Speech Function Realization	Technique	Example
Statement	Declarative Facts	Presenting survey results	(h) "..... <i>Edelman Trust Barometer</i> has just published a survey of public confidence in doing business in Indonesia, it is at a high level, ranking second after China, again, second after China" (clause 37)
		Present facts	(i) "Indonesia's economy grows consistently above 5 percent. Last year we grew 5.3 percent" (clause 38)

In convincing the audience of the importance of investing in Indonesia, he presented logical facts to support his statement. This clause is predominantly delivered in a declarative language style to convey information to the audience and state the most current facts. Based on table 3. the technique used in forming the logos is done by;

- a). Presenting research results,
- b). Present facts.

The first technique used by President Joko Widodo in presenting the Logo is with references that justify the arguments made by presenting research results, for example in (h), he uses the results of a survey conducted by the Edelman Trust

Barometer which states that the level of public trust in running a business is high, ranked second after China. This was used as the basis for President Joko Widodo's argument in convincing investors who attended Ecosperity Week that investment in Indonesia is very promising.

The second technique used by President Jokowi is to present facts as in (i). President Joko Widodo provided information to the audience. He used the clause to support survey results released by the Edelman Trust Barometer. These two techniques make President Joko Widodo's statement acceptable logically and with common sense. The same clause relating to this is also stated in the clause which talks about economic stability and development in Indonesia.

In terms of mood elements, both personal and impersonal subjects are used, such as the Edelman Trust Barometer, China and Indonesia. The words "Edelman Trust Barometer" are used as the subject of the clause to emphasize that Edelman is the party that can emphasize to the audience that Indonesia has a high level of trust in running business. He also used the subject clause "China" to emphasize to the audience that Indonesia has been able to compete with China, which is known as the largest economic country in the world. He also predominantly uses the simple present which shows that it is happening now. He wants to emphasize that what he stated is a fact that is happening now, as in the sentence "In the first quarter of this year we grew 5.03 percent" (clause 40).

President Joko Widodo started the logo clause using additional word elements and a subject. The use of additional words in starting clauses is motivated by two factors. First, he wants to connect the clauses to make them more coherent by using connecting words like "and". Second, he wants to emphasize to the audience the facts represented by the connecting words "state", "atmosphere", "heart" and "comment". Example of the adverb "The trade balance experienced a surplus for 36 consecutive months, last year there was a surplus of USD54.5 billion" (clause 42). President Joko Widodo presented the logo to his audience with a positive polarity. He uses positive polarity when discussing the potential and developments that Indonesia has achieved in developing the capital city of the archipelago which has economic potential.

2. Discussion

In the research conducted, three aspects of SFL were identified in the speech used by President Joko Widodo, including the use of declarative mood, the realization of various functions, and negative and positive polarity in clauses. President Joko Widodo's dominant use of the declarative mood in his speeches shows that he positions himself as a provider of information, not a requester of information. This finding is also obtained from research conducted by (Saputra et al., 2023; Chen, 2016) which states that declarative mood has a high percentage used in speech because its main purpose is to provide information.

President Joko Widodo uses declarative mood to provide information (messages) directly between him and the audience, because declarative mood has the property of forming statements (Halliday, 2014). The declarative mood is used to convey messages without any prior thought process by the audience. In full, the imperative mood used in presidential speeches has the function of inviting listeners to act collectively which he considers to be a solution to the problem (Chen, 2016). President Joko Widodo wants to emphasize that what he said is something concrete and cannot be denied. This is different from the imperative mood which tends to require a

response from the audience to find out whether the proposition conveyed is successful or not (Ayoola, 2012; Halliday, 2014). Not only that, President Joko Widodo uses a declarative mood to make implicit requests to his audience. This realization is one of the non-typical functions of the declarative mood (Eggins, 2004; Halliday, 2014) as exemplified in (e).

The information conveyed by President Joko Widodo was realized through various moods of declarations from all the rhetorical elements of ethos, pathos and logos. In the ethos clause, he emphasizes providing information to the audience that his statement is based on facts found in the field. In the pathos clause, he predominantly uses the declarative mood to build sentimental emotions by evoking the audience's positive and negative feelings. In the logical clause it presents concrete facts published by credible organizations in its field.

The types of mood and realization of speech functions used by President Joko Widodo are also quite varied. In the ethos clause, President Joko Widodo uses a type of declarative mood which has the function of stating facts. In the pathos clause, he uses two types of mood, namely declarative and imperative. The declarative mood in this clause is conveyed with different speech functions, including statements of opinion, statements, and indirect requests. In the imperative mood, he uses it according to its function, namely a direct request. In the logos clause, it only uses one type of mood, namely for a statement of fact.

In general, President Joko Widodo predominantly uses positive polarity in constructing pathos and logos clauses, but in several clauses he uses negative polarity. Positive polarity when he talks about the rapid movement of the Indonesian economy and the potential of the capital city of the archipelago with the resources it has. He tends to use the word "already" in building positive polarity as in "We have prepared..." (clause 29). Kata has shown that he is not just offering wishful thinking but has prepared the things needed to realize mutually beneficial economic cooperation.

The research results show that the persuasive speeches used by President Joko Widodo use various types of mood and realization of functions in his speeches. The use of positive clauses can attract the audience to join in investing in the development of Indonesia's capital city which has great potential. President Joko Widodo's speech also had a controversial side because he directly asked who would lead Indonesia next year who could secure Singapore's investment in Indonesia. This element shows that Singapore and indirectly the Indonesian people must start considering leaders who can support Indonesia's sustainable development.

The implications of this research contain many positive clauses for investment and negative for political opponents who will lead Indonesia in the future. For Joko Widodo's supporters, this criticism will make them believe that the decisions and statements made by Joko Widodo are correct and must be implemented. However, for opponents, this criticism will make them dislike the speaker.

CONCLUSION

President Joko Widodo's speech is qualified as a persuasive speech with the aim of convincing the audience to be persuaded to invest in the capital city of the archipelago as the new capital city of Indonesia. This effort can be seen from the grammatical choices he uses. He created a declarative mood to position himself as a bearer of information directly to the audience. From a grammatical point of view, he uses many

positive clauses and several negative clauses which are quite controversial and contain sentences asking who will lead Indonesia in the future.

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